

Effect of culture medium composition and reuse on the growth of *Porphyridium cruentum*

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Abstract

The aim of this study was to develop a fertiliser-based culture medium to reduce production costs and to enhance the sustainability of producing *Porphyridium cruentum*, a red marine microalga of commercial interest. Additionally, the impact of water recirculation on microalgal growth was assessed. Overall, the results indicated that the nitrogen source significantly affected biomass growth, with sodium nitrate supporting higher biomass productivity ($0.23 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$), surpassing sodium nitrite ($0.18 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$) and ammonium chloride ($0.14 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$). Urea had a negative impact on growth. A N:P molar ratio of 20:1 increased biomass productivity by approximately 24% compared to the lower ratio studied (8:1) while also reducing phosphorus demand. The optimal medium composition was: $1.75 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1} \text{ NaNO}_3$, $0.23 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1} \text{ K}_2\text{HPO}_4\cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $0.04 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1} \text{ CaCl}_2$, $0.49 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1} \text{ MgSO}_4\cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, and $24.0 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1} \text{ Karentol}^\circledast$. Lastly, water reutilisation negatively impacted biomass concentration, promoting the accumulation of extracellular organic carbon and bacteria as well as increasing the viscosity and turbidity of the culture.

Keywords: phycoerythrin, protein, water consumption, biomass, biotechnology, sustainability.

1. Introduction

The expected increase in food demand, coupled with the growing emphasis on sustainability, has led to unconventional and renewable food sources being explored. This includes the utilisation of resources from saltwater, which represents 97.5% of the earth's water [1], as innovative foods or food ingredients. Marine microalgae constitute a key component of saltwater ecosystems [2]. Due to their rapid growth rate, and their capacity to fix atmospheric CO₂, these photosynthetic microorganisms have attracted increasing interest as environmentally sustainable alternatives to several industrial applications [3]. *Porphyridium cruentum*, a Rhodophyta species, is a red spherical unicellular microalga that has potential applications in the food, feed, cosmetics, and pharmaceutical industries [3]. It can be used as a feedstock to produce valuable compounds with technological potential. These include polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs), exopolysaccharides (EPS), and phycobiliproteins (PBs), which exhibit health-promoting properties such as antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and antimicrobial activities [4]. Currently, *P. cruentum* extracts are used in cosmetics formulations such as anti-aging creams, serums, sunscreens, and hair products. In the food sector, its derived compounds - particularly phycobiliproteins and polysaccharides - have shown potential as natural colourants and functional ingredients in a wide range of products, including baked goods, syrups, dairy-based items, jellies, dehydrated foods, fermented milk products, and ice-cream [5,6].

The environmental and operational conditions during biomass production and the culture medium's composition are key factors influencing both the, biomass productivity yield and these specific metabolites' synthesis and accumulation [7]. The culture medium's composition is critically important as it can be used not only to modify the biomass composition [8] but also to avoid the growth of unwanted contaminants [9]. The primary constituents of microalgal biomass include carbon (30-50% dry weight (d.w.)), oxygen (30-50% d.w.), hydrogen (3-7% d.w.), nitrogen (4-9% d.w.), and phosphorus (1-3% d.w.),

along with trace amounts of elements such as sulphur, potassium, magnesium or calcium [10]. Several studies on different strains have shown that the nitrogen source plays an essential role in regulating metabolic processes, directly impacting microalgal growth and biochemical composition [11,12]. Furthermore, the concentration of nutrients, such as the N:P ratio, has an impact on microalgal growth. While nitrogen supports amino acids, nucleotides, and pigments, phosphorus is vital for ATP, nucleic acids, and cell membranes. Any molar ratio disproportion can hinder growth and metabolism [13] or cause an inefficient use of resources. Optimising the nutrient composition and the culture medium concentration allows one to achieve optimal culture performance, while reducing production costs and obtaining greater biomass productivity [14].

Water is another essential component in microalgae cultivation. However, the substantial water requirements associated with microalgae production can pose a challenge when trying to achieve environmental sustainability [15]. Recycling or reusing the exhausted cultivation water after harvesting is currently being investigated as a solution for reducing water and nutrient requirements, enhancing sustainability and reducing associated costs [16]. Nevertheless, research suggests that this process may influence the growth of several strains due to the potential accumulation of salts, bacteria, extracellular products, cell debris, and nutrients, all of which could either inhibit or stimulate growth [17]. In the case of *Arthrospira platensis*, biomass production decreased by 68% after the fourth cycle of medium reuse. This reduction was accompanied by an accumulation of organic matter in the culture medium, with approximately 70% of the accumulated material consisting of polysaccharides [18]. A similar pattern of organic matter accumulation has been observed in *Porphyridium* sp., where the presence of complex exopolysaccharides in the cell walls plays a significant role in altering the culture medium's properties. Throughout the cultivation process, this polysaccharide layer progressively thickens. Over time, it breaks down and is released into the surrounding medium, leading to increased viscosity [19]. Studies have shown that the presence of extracellular substances hinders both microalgal growth and the ability to reuse the culture. When

recirculating the exhausted culture medium, an increase in viscosity was observed. In addition, biological contaminants may accumulate, as the carbohydrates in the exopolysaccharides can serve as a nutrient source for certain microorganisms, such as bacteria [20].

P. cruentum is a strain of commercial interest, offering several unique advantages over other species. This strain stands out for producing a high quantity of phycoerythrin, a fluorescence and stable red phycobiliprotein, ranging from 5 to 10% of its dry weight, surpassing the levels reported in other phycoerythrin-producing algal species. For instance, the cyanobacteria *Anabaena sp.* and *Pseudanabaena sp.* contain approximately 1.23% d.w. [21] and 4.17% d.w. [22], respectively, while red microalgae such as *Gracilaria gracilis* contain 0.09% dw [23]. Additionally, *P. cruentum* synthesizes arachidonic acid, an essential omega-6 polyunsaturated fatty acid involved in the regulation of human metabolism and neurological development, reaching levels of 1.72% d.w. depending on cultivation conditions [24]. In contrast, other commercially used microalgae such as *Chlorella vulgaris* and *Spirulina*, contain no arachidonic acid [25,26]. A further advantage of *P. cruentum* is its capacity to produce exopolysaccharides that exhibit antioxidant, antiviral, and antibacterial activities [27]. The ability to produce exopolysaccharides is considerably higher than that of, for example, *C. vulgaris* (0.36 g·L⁻¹) [28]. These biochemical features highlight the potential of *P. cruentum*, despite the current hurdles of cultivating it at the large-scale, such as its, cultivation requirements and the challenges faced in its downstream processing. To explore its suitability for future large-scale applications, it is necessary to identify novel, robust, and fast-growing strains, and to optimise their production process through preliminary studies conducted at the laboratory scale. This study aimed to develop a novel, inexpensive culture medium for producing *P. cruentum* and to assess the effect of this novel medium on biomass composition. The study was carried out using 250 mL bubble columns and the results were compared against F/2 [29] and ASW media [30], both widely investigated in the scientific literature [21]. In addition, the potential of reusing the exhausted culture medium

without prior treatment was preliminarily evaluated. This was done to determine whether medium recirculation would improve or affect biomass yield in this strain, thereby providing a basis for future studies focused on achieving the circular economy principles of sustainable cultivation and economic efficiency, at the same time as optimising biomass yield.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Strain used

The microalga used was *P. cruentum* SAG 1380-1A (GenBank: MT483997.1). The inoculum was produced using 1 L bubble columns with pH (pH 8.0), light ($350 \mu\text{m photons}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$) and temperature (22 °C) control. The culture medium consisted of 30 $\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ marine salt, 0.8 $\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ $\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2\cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 0.1 $\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ KH_2PO_4 , 0.35 $\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ $\text{MgSO}_4\cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, and 20 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ of micronutrients (Karentol[®] Mix Super, Kenogard, Spain). Except where stated otherwise, this micronutrient mix was used in all the different media studied. Its composition (according to the manufacturer) comprises: boron, as boron ethanolamine 0.70% (w/w); copper chelated by ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) and complexed by heptagluconic acid (HGA) 0.30% (w/w); iron chelated by EDDHSA/EDTA and complexed by HGA 7.00% (w/w); manganese chelated by EDTA and complexed by HGA 3.30% (w/w); molybdenum, as sodium salt 0.10% (w/w); and zinc chelated by EDTA and complexed by HGA 0.60% (w/w).

2.2. Biomass production

The biomass production was carried out using 300 mL bubble-columns as described in previous studies [31] with some modifications. Briefly, the operating volume was 250 mL and aeration was constant at 0.2 v/v/min. The pH was controlled at 8.0 by the on-demand injection of pure carbon dioxide and the culture temperature was set and controlled at 25 ± 2 °C. The irradiance reaching the culture's surface was $800 \mu\text{m photons}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ and a

light:dark regime of 10:14 h was used. Biomass production was carried out with each photobioreactor serving as an independent experimental unit.

All the prepared media had a sea salt concentration of $30 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ and contained agricultural-grade reagents (fertilisers). The composition of the different culture media evaluated is detailed in Table 1, where the naming of each medium follows a systematic nomenclature reflecting its nutrient composition. The letter (e.g., A, B, C, D) indicates the type of nitrogen source used. Once the optimal nitrogen source was identified, the number that follows (e.g., 8 or 12) refers to the nitrogen-phosphorus (N:P) molar ratio applied. Finally, Roman numeral suffixes (e.g., I, II, III) indicate further modifications in nutrient composition, such as adjusted concentrations of phosphate, magnesium, or micronutrients. The nutrient sources (fertilisers) were provided by a local retailer. The cost of the different compounds was estimated as: NaNO_3 , $5.3 \text{ €}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$; NH_4Cl , $4.2 \text{ €}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$; NaNO_2 , $7.8 \text{ €}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$, $\text{CH}_4\text{N}_2\text{O}$, $1.2 \text{ €}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$; K_2HPO_4 , $11.5 \text{ €}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$; $\text{MgSO}_4\cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $1.8 \text{ €}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$; CaCl_2 , $3.7 \text{ €}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$; and micronutrients approximately $11.0 \text{ €}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$.

The first step in developing the culture medium was to identify the optimal nitrogen source. Therefore, the first set of experiments were designed to study the influence of five different nitrogen sources on growth: (A) sodium nitrate, (B1 and B2) ammonium chloride, (C) sodium nitrite, and (D) urea. All the media used in this first set of experiments were formulated based on the Redfield molar ratio (N:P, 16:1). Although different nitrogen source compounds were employed in media A to D, the total nitrogen concentration was standardized across all treatments to ensure comparability. Variations in the mass concentrations ($\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) of each nitrogen source were solely due to differences in the molecular weights and nitrogen content, without altering the actual amount of nitrogen supplied. The only exception was ammonium chloride, for which a lower nitrogen concentration (B1) was included to evaluate its effect.

Following the identification of the optimal nitrogen source, four cultures were developed to investigate the effect of varying the N:P molar ratio: (A8) 8:1, (A12) 12:1, (A16) 16:1,

and (A20) 20:1. The nitrogen concentration was kept constant while the phosphorus concentration was adjusted.

A third set of trials aimed at reducing the excess of nutrients was carried out in a stepwise manner. First, nitrogen content was reduced, followed by calcium, then micronutrients, and finally magnesium. In this context, the following reductions were applied:

- The NaNO_3 content was reduced by 30%, from 2.50 to 1.75 $\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$.
- The CaCl_2 content was reduced by 90 or 95%, from 0.40 $\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ to 0.04 or 0.02 $\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$, respectively.
- Micronutrients content was reduced by 20, 50, or 80%, from 30 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ to 24, 15, or 6 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$, respectively,
- The $\text{MgSO}_4\cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ content was reduced by 20, 50 or 80%, from 0.61 $\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ to 0.49, 0.31, or 0.12 $\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$, respectively.

Also, a different source of micronutrients Crop Mix[®] E Plus (Cropfutura, Almería, Spain), was tested to compare the effects on growth. According to the manufacturer, it's composition is: boron 0.70% (w/w); copper chelated by ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) 0.30% (w/w); iron chelated by EDDHA 3.50% (w/w); manganese chelated by EDTA 4.00% (w/w); molybdenum 0.30% (w/w); and zinc chelated by EDTA 0.70% (w/w). All the culture medium formulations are detailed in Table 1. The optimised medium was compared with other media, namely F/2 and ASW, which are widely used in the literature to produce this microalga at the laboratory scale.

Finally, this study also aimed to evaluate the feasibility of reusing the exhausted culture medium. Different recirculation rates (0%, 25%, 50%, and 75%) were investigated. Briefly, different percentages of the exhausted culture medium were used in combination with sterile distilled water to start a new production run. Initially, microalgae were cultured in batch mode without recirculation until the stationary phase. Then, the biomass was harvested by centrifugation and the supernatant was collected and reused. Each recirculation percentage was assessed during three consecutive production runs. The nutrient content of the exhausted media was determined, and fresh nutrients were added

to achieve the composition of the optimised medium. All the trials were carried out in triplicate.

2.3. Growth monitoring

Samples from the bubble columns were collected daily during the tests to analyse the maximum quantum PSII yield (F_v/F_m) and algal growth. A lightweight hand-held fluorometer AquaPen AP110/C (Photon System Instruments, Drásov, Czech Republic) was used to determine the photochemical efficiency of PSII after a 15-min dark-adaption period. The algal growth was monitored through optical density reading at 560, 565, 620, 650, 680, and 750 nm using a UV-Visible Spectrophotometer Genesys 150 (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Inc, MA, USA). A calibration curve was made using the known dry-weight concentrations of the microalga and the above-mentioned optical densities. The cell concentration was determined by filtering 30 mL of culture through a pre-weighted 0.45 μm glass-fibre filter, washed with 30 mL of distilled water and then dried at 80 °C until a constant weight was achieved [32].

2.3.1 Physicochemical determinations

The supernatant was obtained by centrifugation using a Digicen 22 centrifuge (Ortoalresa, Madrid, Spain) at 5000 rpm for 15 min. For the nitrate and phosphorus determinations, both the initial and exhausted media were analysed following the standard official methods approved by the Spanish Ministry of Agriculture, as previously previously [33]. Briefly, the nitrate concentration was determined by measuring absorbance at 220 nm and 275 nm with the nitrate standard for IC 74246, while the phosphate (PO_4^{3-}) concentration was determined with the vanado-molybdate complex using the phosphate standard for IC 38364. All the analytical determinations were performed in triplicate.

Following a 10-fold dilution, the supernatant's non-purgeable organic carbon (NPOC) was determined using a TOC-VCPH total organic carbon analyser equipped with an ASI-V autosampler (Shimadzu, Tokyo, Japan). The supernatant's turbidity was measured

using a microprocessor turbidity meter HI 93703 (Hanna Instruments, RI, USA). In addition, the fluid's viscosity was assessed using a Brookfield DV-II+ viscometer (Brookfield Engineering, MA, USA). All these determinations were performed in triplicate. To monitor mesophilic aerobic bacterial growth, the supernatants from each treatment were diluted using PBS solution (Merck KGaA, Darmstadt, Germany) pH 7.4 and subsequently plated in plate count agar (Fisher Scientific S.L., Madrid, Spain) prepared with sea salts ($30 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$), followed by 24 h of incubation at $37 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Plates with PBS solution (but no inoculation) were used as the negative control.

2.3.2 Biomass composition

The wet pellet obtained by centrifugation was frozen, freeze-dried, and stored at $-20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for subsequent biochemical analysis. The total nitrogen content of the biomass was determined using an ELEMENTAR Vario Micro CHNS elemental analyser (Elementar Analysensysteme GmbH, Hanau, Germany), following the 2mgChem80s method provided by the manufacturer. The total protein content was estimated using a nitrogen-to-protein conversion factor for microalgae of 4.78, as reported in several studies [34,35]. Lipids were quantified according to the official standard method UNE-EN 17908:2024 based on the Ryckebosch-Foubert method [36]. The total ash content was determined by combusting 0.2 g of sample in a muffle furnace at $575 \pm 25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 7 h. Moisture was estimated by drying 2 g of sample at $80 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in an air flow oven until a constant weight was achieved. The total carbohydrate content was calculated by difference.

Finally, phycobiliprotein crude extracts were obtained by grinding 0.5 g of biomass with an equal weight of aluminium oxide for 6 min to facilitate cell wall disruption. The resultant powder was suspended in 10 mL of 100 mM phosphate buffer (pH 6) and homogenised using a vortex for 30 s. The samples were kept under agitation at $22 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in the dark for 24 h before being centrifuged at 5000 rpm for 15 min. The supernatant was collected by centrifugation, and the procedure was repeated using the obtained pellet. The phycobiliprotein content, composed of B-phycoerythrin (B-PE), R-phycoerythrin (R-PE), R-phycoerythrin (R-PC),

and allophycocyanin (APC), was determined by spectrophotometry, measuring absorbance at 565, 620, and 650 nm and calculated using the equations reported in previous work [37]. Analytical determinations were done in triplicate.

2.4. Statistical analysis

The results are expressed as mean values ($n=3$) \pm standard deviation (SD). Data were analysed through a one-way analysis of variance and a Fisher's LSD post hoc test ($p<0.05$) using Statgraphics Centurion v19 (Statgraphics Technologies Inc., VA, US).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Medium optimisation

Figure 1 shows the effect of different nitrogen sources on the biomass concentration, Fv/Fm value, and productivity of *P. cruentum* over time. Overall, sodium nitrate (Medium A) exhibited the highest biomass concentration, reaching approximately $3.5 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ after 14 days, followed by sodium nitrite (Medium C, $2.3 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) ($p<0.05$). The ammonium chloride treatments (B1 and B2) resulted in lower biomass concentrations (approximately $1.5 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$; $p<0.05$). Urea (Medium D) also impacted negatively on growth ($p<0.05$). The photosynthetic efficiency shown in Figure 1B remained stable (Fv/Fm, 0.5-0.6) in the cultures produced using sodium nitrate, sodium nitrite, and ammonium chloride. At the same time, the Fv/Fm of the culture with urea declined after day 4 ($p<0.05$), indicating physiological stress, and in concordance with the low biomass concentration. The biomass productivity of the microalgae obtained from the different treatments showed a significant statistical difference ($p<0.05$) between treatments with a nitrate source (Medium A; $0.23 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$) and the other sources, for which the obtained values were 0.18, 0.14-0.08 $\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$, and while there was no growth for the treatments with sodium nitrite, ammonium chloride, and urea, respectively (Figure 1C). These trends align with the biomass accumulation and the photosynthetic efficiency observed, reinforcing nitrate

as being the optimal nitrogen source for *P. cruentum* cultivation. The biomass concentration obtained in this study when using nitrate as the nitrogen source was higher than that reported in a previous work [37]. The authors of that study observed a biomass concentration of $2.5 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ after 18 days. It was also higher than the biomass concentration obtained for *Porphyridium purpureum*, which ranged from 0.34 to $0.95 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$, after 28 days of growth [38]. These results indicate that the selected nutrient compounds and nitrate promote *P. cruentum* growth. Nitrate has proven to be the most appropriate nitrogen source for most strains. For instance, the microalga *Tetraselmis* sp. grew better when produced using nitrate ($1.45 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) compared to ammonium ($0.98 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) [39]. Similarly, the microalga *Chlorella zofingiensis* reached approximately $2.0 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ with nitrate, and $1.5 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ with urea, after 17 days [40]. The reason for this higher growth can be attributed to the predominance of nitrate in the environment and a possible strain-specific adaptation to this dominant nitrogen source [41]. Moreover, ammonium can be toxic for some strains, given that the most toxic form of ammoniacal nitrogen directly impacts the photosynthetic apparatus. Indeed, at a concentration of $100 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ of ammonium, *Spirulina platensis* biomass remained stable with no significant increase for the first six days, followed by a subsequent decline. In contrast, at $200 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$, a reduction in biomass was observed as early as the second day [42]. On the other hand, [43], observed that the *Porphyridium* strain needed substantial adaptation and 34 days using urea at $0.75 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ to grow successfully, indicating both a limited uptake and inefficient assimilation of urea-derived nitrogen. In the present study, the low growth rates and physiological stress observed when using urea are likely attributable to urea hydrolysis, which leads to ammonium accumulation. Ammonium assimilation is often hindered by the suboptimal activity of key enzymes, such as glutamine synthetase and glutamate synthase, resulting in poor post-uptake growth efficiency and impaired pigment biosynthesis, which in turns leads to cell bleaching and growth arrest. Furthermore, excessive intracellular ammonium accumulation may cause oxidative stress, disrupting enzymatic activity, promoting lipid peroxidation, and leading to cellular dysfunction [42].

Although the medium with sodium nitrate shows a higher cost per m³ (Table 1), the biomass productivity achieved was the highest. In addition, nitrate proved to be metabolically more favourable and less toxic than ammonium and urea, contributing to more stable growth conditions and potentially higher cell viability in large-scale systems. Moreover, Medium A still allowed for nutrient optimisation, particularly in reducing the nitrogen content, which represents the 67% of the medium's cost, offering potential for cost optimization.

The second set of tests aimed at identifying the optimal N:P molar ratio. The results from these tests are detailed in Figure 2. The biomass concentration showed a similar growth trend across all treatments until day 10. After that point, the N:P ratio of 20:1 achieved the highest biomass concentration (4.5 g·L⁻¹ at day 15), followed by the control treatment using the Redfield ratio (3.8 g·L⁻¹) ($p < 0.05$). The treatments with N:P ratios of 8:1 and 12:1 exhibited slightly lower biomass concentrations (around 3.2 g·L⁻¹). As shown in Figure 2B, the photochemical efficiency of PSII remained stable (0.45-0.55) across all treatments, indicating the absence of severe physiological stress. The biomass productivity of each treatment is illustrated in Figure 1C. The results indicate that the biomass productivity achieved when using an N:P ratio of 20:1 was on average 24% higher than the lower ratios, with statistically significant differences ($p < 0.05$). When using this ratio, the culture had a productivity of 0.26 g·L⁻¹·day⁻¹, outperforming Media A8, A12, and A16, which had productivity values of 0.21, 0.20 and 0.21 g·L⁻¹·day⁻¹, respectively ($p < 0.05$). Similar results were obtained in previous studies [44], in which the highest biomass concentration (1.2 g·L⁻¹ after 10 days of cultivation) was reached at the highest N:P ratios tested (35:1-50:1). Moreover, a different study reported that the cell concentration of *Nannochloropsis oculata* reached 6.5 · 10⁶ cell·mL⁻¹ and 9.5 · 10⁶ cell·mL⁻¹ when cultivated with molar N:P ratios of 5:1 and 20:1, respectively [45]. These findings suggest that A20 Medium with N:P 20:1, provides favourable nutrient conditions and improves biomass productivity. Additionally, this treatment has the significant advantage

of using 20% less initial phosphorus. Several studies have shown that reduced phosphorus levels may enhance the biomass yield of *P. cruentum* [46]. This can be attributed to the fact that, under elevated phosphorus conditions, the nutrient uptake balance can be disrupted; in fact, microalgae may engage in luxury phosphorus uptake, wherein cells absorb phosphorus above their immediate metabolic requirements. Consequently, this phenomenon can modulate physiological processes such as nitrogen assimilation pathways [47]. *P. cruentum* has been reported to tolerate higher N:P ratios (50:1) due to its low phosphorous demand [48]. This study constrained the ratio to 20:1 to avoid potential phosphorous deficiency. With nitrogen held constant, raising the N:P ratio would require reducing phosphorous availability to nearly zero. This would impair critical metabolic functions, particularly ATP synthesis, nucleic acid formation, and membrane stability [13].

Once the optimal nitrogen source and N:P molar ratio were identified, the next production runs aimed to reduce the nutrient input. Not all the nutrients supplied were consumed. Indeed, the concentrations of nitrogen and phosphorus in the exhausted A20 medium were 74.2 and 30.7 mg·L⁻¹, respectively. Different media were formulated maintaining the N:P ratio - their effect on growth is shown in Figure 3. One can observe that a 30% reduction in the nitrogen content had no effect on growth, consequently treatment A20-I will be used as the control treatment from now on. This reduction in the nitrogen content, with had no effect on growth, led to approximately a 26% reduction in the medium's cost (Table 1). In the following trials, a 90% reduction in the initial CaCl₂ concentration did not affect the biomass productivity, as can be seen in Figure 3A. A 95% reduction in CaCl₂ resulted in a drop of approximately 50% in the biomass concentration ($p < 0.05$). The results shown in Figure 3B suggest that MgSO₄·7H₂O concentrations that were 20 and 50% of those in the control medium composition resulted in lower biomass productivities. The productivity decreased by 48 and 41% when the MgSO₄·7H₂O concentrations were reduced by 80 and 50%, respectively ($p < 0.05$). Similarly, it has been shown that

increasing the magnesium concentration had a beneficial impact on the biomass yield of *C. vulgaris*. [49]. These findings can be explained by previous studies in which it was shown that calcium ions are involved in cell growth and intracellular metabolic signalling pathways [50]; while magnesium plays a critical role in sustaining autotrophic photosynthesis, serving both as the central atom in chlorophyll molecules and as an activator of essential enzymes, including ribulose 1,5-bisphosphate carboxylase/oxygenase [51]. Therefore, a limitation in these compounds is associated with a diminished microalgal growth rate. Similar results were obtained in the following steps, where a 20% reduction in the concentration of micronutrients did not affect biomass productivity (Figure 3C). These results indicate that the presence of an adequate concentration of bioavailable minerals in the medium is required to sustain an optimal *P. cruentum* growth rate. Finally, Figure 3D shows the biomass productivity obtained after replacing the micronutrient source. The results indicate no significant difference between using Karentol® Mix Super and Crop Mix® E Plus.

Based on the results described above, the optimal culture medium selected was A20-IX: 1.75 g·L⁻¹ NaNO₃, 0.23 g·L⁻¹ K₂HPO₄·3H₂O, 0.04 g·L⁻¹ CaCl₂, 0.49 g·L⁻¹ MgSO₄·7H₂O, and 24.0 mg·L⁻¹ of Karentol®.

3.2. Biomass composition

As shown in Figure 4, A20-IX medium and ASW medium exhibited the highest biomass productivity, with values above 0.23 g·L⁻¹·day⁻¹. ASW medium requires a greater nutrient supply, which may influence its cost-effectiveness and sustainability in large-scale applications. Biomass produced using F/2 medium resulted in a yellow colouration, likely due to the low nitrogen concentration (0.0123 g·L⁻¹). This is consistent with the findings reported in a previous study [52] in which *P. purpureum* cultures grown using 0.049 g·L⁻¹ of nitrogen displayed a yellow hue, while cultures with higher nitrogen concentrations (0.083 g·L⁻¹ and 0.25 g·L⁻¹) exhibited orange and red-violet hues, respectively. The low

concentration and colour change can be attributed to nitrogen limitation, which decreases NADPH availability, compromising amino acid biosynthesis, and consequently results in diminished cellular growth and protein production [53]. F/2 medium led to a lower biomass productivity of $0.12 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$ ($p<0.05$). Furthermore, the nutritional profile of *P. cruentum* cultured in the optimised medium (as the percentage of free ash dry weight) was 30% total proteins, including 1.46% R-PC, 2.19% APC, and 6.16% B-PE, along with 35% lipids and 35% carbohydrates. The protein content was comparable to that reported in a previous work, in which the protein concentration obtained after manual grinding of the biomass was 25% [54]. Notably, the biomass produced using A20-IX had a significantly higher B-PE content than the values reported previously, surpassing 4.01% in *P. cruentum* [37] and 3.05% in *P. purpureum* [55]. Additionally, the optimised medium favoured B-PE production, reaching concentrations that were 2-fold higher than those achieved with ASW medium ($p<0.05$). When using ASW, the macromolecular composition of the biomass was 20% total proteins with 0.80% of R-PC, 1.06% APC, and 3.07% B-PE. In addition, the biomass produced using ASW had 37% lipids and 43% carbohydrates. When *P. cruentum* was cultured in F/2 medium, it exhibited the lowest total nitrogen content, with out-of-range nitrogen values, while at the same time having the highest lipid concentration, at approximately 64.74% (expressed as the percentage of free ash dry weight). The much higher lipid content can be attributed to the medium's low nitrogen concentration. This aligns with previous studies which showed that inducing microalgae to nutrient stress, mainly nitrogen, is an effective strategy for promoting lipid accumulation [53,56]. This occurs because of nitrogen limitation, which reduces both photosynthetic efficiency and nitrogen assimilation, thereby redirecting carbon partitioning towards synthesising storage compounds such as lipids and carbohydrates [57]. However, such a strategy results in low biomass productivity [58]. Overall, these findings suggest that the optimised medium is well-suited for *P. cruentum* biomass production. Additionally, the nutrient concentration promoted B-PE synthesis and accumulation. These results are promising as B-PE is a

high-value bioactive compound and the concentrations achieved using the A20-IX medium were higher than those obtained using F/2 or ASW.

3.3. Water reutilisation

Finally, this study aimed to assess the potential reutilisation of the exhausted culture medium. Different recirculation percentages were investigated, the results of which are shown in Figure 5. Overall, the culture medium reutilisation had a negative effect on growth ($p < 0.05$). The highest biomass concentration was achieved when the biomass was produced using fresh A20-IX medium, prepared using distilled water ($p < 0.05$). As the recirculation increased (25, 50, and 75%), the biomass concentration decreased after three batch cycles, as shown in Figure 5. Comparable findings were observed in a previous study [59], where *Chlorella* sp. and *Navicula* sp. presented a slight decrease in cell concentration when reusing medium. *Staurosira* sp. suffered significant growth inhibition by the second cycle of medium reuse while progressively accumulating dissolved organic carbon. Similarly, another study found that *S. platensis* biomass, produced without recirculation, reached a concentration of $2.8 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$, approximately 5 times higher than in groups with recycled culture medium [60]. To assess the reason for the observed decrease in biomass growth, the quality of the medium was measured, the results of which are summarised in Figure 6. As the recirculation percentages increased, greater accumulation of organic carbon was observed in the medium ($p < 0.05$). The presence of organic carbon can be attributed to the absence of rigid cellulose microfibrils in the cell walls of *Porphyridium* sp., which are instead encased in a mucilage composed of sulphated polysaccharides [61]. As they grow, the outer portion of this polysaccharide matrix gradually dissolves into the surrounding liquid medium. These extracellular polysaccharides are heteropolymers, primarily made up of d-xylose, d- and l-galactose, and d-glucose [62]. Therefore, when recirculating the medium in each cycle, these compounds accumulate over time.

Similarly, the bacteria concentration in the medium increased along with the recirculation percentage ($p < 0.05$). The main reason for this higher bacterial load is the higher organic content, one of the main requirements for bacterial growth. The higher total organic carbon content in the medium also led to higher viscosity and turbidity ($p < 0.05$). These two parameters have a striking effect on microalgal growth. The former is directly linked to mass transfer and the latter to light availability. Increased viscosity can hinder mixing and gas-liquid mass transfer in the culture. It is mainly caused by the accumulation of extracellular metabolites, principally of the sulphated exopolysaccharides excreted by the microalgae. According to the literature, elevated viscosity limits the diffusion of essential gases such as CO_2 and O_2 , negatively impacting key physiological processes, including photosynthesis and respiration. It also reduces bubble mobility and the interfacial area available for gas exchange, and promotes bubble coalescence, further reducing efficiency [63]. Moreover, light availability can be compromised by turbidity. Turbidity blocks and scatters light, preventing it from reaching the cells and therefore reducing photosynthetic activity [64].

Overall, implementing water recirculation could significantly reduce water and nutrient requirements, thus enhancing sustainability and lowering related costs. Pre-treatment strategies to enable the reuse of the exhausted medium are being investigated. Novel, inexpensive strategies to mitigate the inhibitory effects caused by culture medium deterioration need to be explored. These include the use of activated carbon filtration [65], microfiltration [66], or combined techniques such as membrane filtration-electrolysis-ultraviolet systems [67]. Their development and optimisation will be explored in future research.

A cost-effective formulation was developed using agricultural-grade fertilisers and reducing the nutrients concentration without affecting growth. However, the productivities reported in this study are not representative of the industrial scale. For example, a previous work carried out using *N. oculata* demonstrated a decrease in productivity from

0.092 to 0.076 g·L⁻¹·day⁻¹ upon scaling up from 250 mL culture to a 20 L spherical photobioreactor despite the use of an optimised medium [69]. The upscaling of the process to larger scales will face other challenges including limited gas exchange, light distribution, and mixing efficiency, key factor for autotrophic microalgal growth. Moreover, nutrient delivery strategies at industrial scale must be carefully optimised. While reducing nutrient concentration effectively lowered medium costs, precise control is required to avoid nutrient limitation or imbalance. Continuous or semi-continuous nutrient feeding may be necessary to maintain a stable growth. Semi-continuous cultivation mode, commonly used in microalgae production, involves the periodic replacement of a portion of the exhausted medium with fresh medium to sustain nutrient availability and biomass productivity [72]. Feedback-regulated dosing systems are recommended to maintain optimal N:P ratios and prevent physiological stress.

4. Conclusions

This study has determined the composition of an optimised culture medium for *P. cruentum* cultivation. The findings indicate that sodium nitrate proved to be an effective nitrogen source outperforming sodium nitrite, ammonium chloride, and urea, all of which negatively affected growth. Additionally, a nitrogen-to-phosphorus molar ratio of 20:1 maximised biomass productivity compared to lower ratios, allowing one to simultaneously promote growth and reduce phosphorus inputs. Based on these findings, the final culture medium, comprising 1.75 g·L⁻¹ NaNO₃, 0.23 g·L⁻¹ K₂HPO₄·3H₂O, 0.04 g·L⁻¹ CaCl₂, 0.49 g·L⁻¹ MgSO₄·7H₂O, and 24.0 mg·L⁻¹ of Karentol[®], yielded the highest biomass productivity (0.23 g·L⁻¹·day⁻¹) on the seventh day of cultivation.

Using the optimisation process, the final culture medium proved to be suitable for *P. cruentum* growth while significantly reducing the need for nutrients. The optimised culture medium composition also promoted greater B-PE production compared to conventional media evaluated in the scientific literature. The potential reutilisation of the culture

medium was investigated. This strategy led to a decrease in biomass growth. Therefore, further research into effective pre-treatment strategies for recirculating the medium is essential to enhance biomass production and to reduce resource consumption. Implementing such strategies would contribute to a more resource-efficient and sustainable cultivation approach.

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Declaration of interests

The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare

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1 **Table 1. Composition of the culture media**

	Medium*								
Nutrient	A (A16)	B1	B2	C	D	A8	A12	A20	A20-I
NaNO ₃ (g·L ⁻¹)	2.5	-	-	-	-	2.5	2.5	2.5	1.75
NH ₄ Cl (g·L ⁻¹)	-	0.52	1.57	-	-	-	-	-	-
NaNO ₂ (g·L ⁻¹)	-	-	-	2.01	-	-	-	-	-
CH ₄ N ₂ O (g·L ⁻¹)	-	-	-	-	0.87	-	-	-	-
K ₂ HPO ₄ ·3H ₂ O (g·L ⁻¹)	0.41	0.14	0.41	0.41	0.41	0.84	0.56	0.33	0.23
MgSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O (g·L ⁻¹)	0.61	0.61	0.61	0.61	0.61	0.61	0.61	0.61	0.61
CaCl ₂ (g·L ⁻¹)	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.4
Micronutrients (mg·L ⁻¹) ^a	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
Micronutrients (mg·L ⁻¹) ^b	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Estimated cost (€·m ⁻³) ^c	19.8	6.3	13.1	22.1	7.6	23.6	21.1	19.1	14.2
	Medium								
Nutrient	A20-II	A20-III	A20-IV	A20-V	A20-VI	A20-VII	A20-VIII	A20-IX	A20-X
NaNO ₃ (g·L ⁻¹)	1.75	1.75	1.75	1.75	1.75	1.75	1.75	1.75	1.75
NH ₄ Cl (g·L ⁻¹)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
NaNO ₂ (g·L ⁻¹)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
CH ₄ N ₂ O (g·L ⁻¹)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
K ₂ HPO ₄ ·3H ₂ O (g·L ⁻¹)	0.23	0.23	0.23	0.23	0.23	0.23	0.23	0.23	0.23
MgSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O (g·L ⁻¹)	0.61	0.61	0.61	0.61	0.61	0.12	0.31	0.49	0.49
CaCl ₂ (g·L ⁻¹)	0.04	0.02	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04
Micronutrients (mg·L ⁻¹) ^a	30	30	6	15	24	24	24	24	-
Micronutrients (mg·L ⁻¹) ^b	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	24
Estimated cost (€·m ⁻³) ^c	12.9	12.8	12.6	12.7	12.8	12.0	12.3	12.6	12.6

2 * Media labelled A, B, C, or D were prepared using nitrate, ammonium, nitrite, or urea,
3 respectively. In the nitrate-based media (A-series), Arabic numerals indicate the N:P
4 molar ratio. Roman numerals following A20 denote specific modifications made to the
5 A20 medium.

6 ^a Karentol[®] Mix Super (Kenogard, Barcelona, Spain); ^b Crop Mix[®] E Plus (Cropfutura,
7 Almeria, Spain); ^c cost of producing 1 m³ of culture medium.

8 **Figure legends**

9 **Figure 1. Effect of the nitrogen source on (A) the biomass concentration, (B) Fv/Fm**
10 **ratio, and (C) biomass productivity of *P. cruentum*. Values represent the mean**
11 **value of three independent determinations \pm SD. The composition of the culture**
12 **media is described in Table 1. Briefly, media labelled A, B, C, or D were prepared**
13 **using nitrate, ammonium, nitrite, or urea, respectively. Medium B1 differ from**
14 **medium B2 in the N-NH₄⁺ concentration (lower in B1).**

15

16 **Figure 2. Effect of the molar N:P ratio on (A) the growth, (B) Fv/Fm value, and (C)**
17 **biomass productivity of *P. cruentum*. Values represent the mean value of three**
18 **independent determinations \pm SD. The composition of the culture media is**
19 **described in Table 1. Briefly, all the media were formulated using nitrate and the**
20 **Arabic numerals indicate the N:P molar ratio (ranging from 8 to 20).**

21

22 **Figure 3. Effect of reducing the nutrient concentration on the biomass productivity**
23 **of *P. cruentum*. Values represent the mean value of three independent**
24 **determinations \pm SD. The composition of the culture media is abbreviated in the**
25 **figure and detailed in Table 1. Briefly, all media were based on nitrate as the**
26 **nitrogen source with an N:P molar ratio of 20:1. Roman numerals indicate specific**
27 **modifications to the composition of medium A20: Media I-X had a 30% reduction**
28 **in both nitrogen and phosphorus concentrations; Media II-X also had a 90%**
29 **reduction in calcium, except medium III, which had a 95% reduction; Media IV and**
30 **V had micronutrient concentrations reduced by 80 and 50%, respectively; Media**
31 **VI-X had micronutrient concentrations reduced by 20%; Media VII, VIII and IX had**
32 **magnesium concentrations reduced by 80, 50, and 20%, respectively; Media IX and**
33 **X were identical in composition except for the source of micronutrients used.**

34

35

36 **Figure 4. Effect of water re-utilization on the growth of *P. cruentum*. Values**
37 **represent the mean value of three independent determinations \pm SD. The**
38 **composition of medium A20-IX is described in Table 1. F/2 and ASW were standard**
39 **media; their composition is available in the literature [29, 30].**

40

41 **Figure 5. (A) Total organic carbon, (B) viscosity, (C) turbidity, and (D) total aerobic**
42 **mesophylls of the exhausted media. Values represent the mean value of three**
43 **independent determinations \pm SD.**

44

45 **Figure 6. Effects of the culture media on *P. cruentum* biomass productivity. Values**
46 **represent the mean value of three independent determinations \pm SD. NPOC refers**
47 **to non-purgeable organic carbon.**

48 **Figure 1**

49 **Figure 2 (A)**

(B)

(C)

50 **Figure 3**

51

52

53 **Figure 4**

54

55

56 **Figure 5**

57

58 **Figure 6**

59